
More than Ornamental Plants: Plants with significant properties

Revathi Swamy

KES Shroff College of Arts and Commerce, Mumbai -400067, Maharashtra, India.

ABSTRACT

This review paper purpose is to acknowledge the significant properties of plants which are majorly known for its ornamental properties, but also has medicinal to ecological value. Mast tree for instance is a tree which is planted almost near very garden and streets in India, as its roughly triangular and acts as a perfect fence tree, people are not aware of the strong medicinal properties and ecological value as the tree is the host plant of two butterfly species, they plant ornamental plants for beautification or adding aesthetic value to a piece of land, considering to make their piece of land to look good, but often are not aware or unwilling to know the magical properties of such beautiful plants. This paper concentrates the pharmaceutical properties of the plant, some plants are considered have unique flowers, leaves, textures, having unique odour found south Asian countries and some are native to India. The plants mentioned below are planted in the landscape without knowing ecological properties and hence this paper will help to acknowledge the other properties of plant to the society and will be used for other purposes as well.

Keyword: Ornamental plants, Medicinal properties

*Corresponding Author Email: revathiswamy1809@gmail.com
Received 01 April 2023, Accepted 30 April 2023

Please cite this article as: Swamy., More than Ornamental Plants: Plants with significant properties. American Journal of Pharmacy & Health Research 2023.

INTRODUCTION

NIGHT JASMINE

Nyctanthes arbor-tristis

Family: Oleaceae; Nyctanthaceae.

Habitat: Outer Himalaya, Assam, West Bengal; cultivated in many parts of India.

English: Tree of Sorrow, Night Jasmine, Coral Jasmine.

Local: पारिजात, हरसिंगार, रात की रानी, शेफाली, शिउली

Ayurvedic: Paarijaata, Shephaali, Shephaalikaa, Mandaara.

Dose: Leaf - 10-20 ml juice.

General description:

Origin from India and is planted often near the tulsi plant. It's an evergreen, erect shrub or tree. The plant height is up to 4 to 6 meters and has a width of 2-4 meters. Flowers open towards the evening to night and drop the next morning. Flowers in flushes throughout the year

Figure 1: Night Jasmine

Silvicultural characteristics:

It requires sun growing, semi shade lighting and Normal water. Can tolerate less and also can tolerate more, which makes the plant easy to grow. Fertile and having good drainage soil will be preferred.

Chemical constituents:

The seeds and the leaves contain iridoid glycosides. The leaf contains mannitol, beta-amyrin, beta- sitosterol, hentriacontane, benzoic acid, astragaln, nicotiflorin, oleanolic acid, nyctanthic acid, friedelin and lupeol. The seeds of the plant contain a polysaccharide glucomannan. (*Easy Ayurveda*)

Medicinal use:

They are used to treat constipation also as a remedy for snake bites. In Ayurveda, parijat leaves do wonder, treats various types of fever, cough, arthritis, worm infections. Hard or decoction treats arthritis, constipation, worm infection. They are also good as cosmetics to treat hair loss and recovery of the scalp, and also in skin recovery. Sure remedy from common cough and cold to arthritis. (*Floweraura*)

Night Jasmine

Flower

This small, fragrant, white flowers works wonderfully for gastric complaints and respiratory complaints.

Stem

Stem are powdered as a remedy for joint pains and knee pain

Leaves

Effective relief in the treatment of common cough and cold, inflammation and fever. Juice of leaves have antibacterial and anti-inflammatory, mixed with sugar to treat stomach diseases of children, dried leaves are used as Assamese food dishes.

GARDEN RUE

Ruta graveolens

Family: Rutaceae.

Habitat: Native to Mediterranean region; cultivated all over India.

English: Garden Rue.

Local: सितबा

Figure 2: Garden Rue

General description:

Small herb with ovate leaves and beautiful yellow flowers bloom through the plant. Rue is used for other painful conditions including headache and also cramps

Silvicultural characteristics:

It is drought tolerant. Rue herb does well in well-drained soil. It needs full sun to grow well.

Chemical constituents:

Contains a volatile oil, with 2-undecanone-2-nonanone, 2-nonyl acetate, psoralen, and bergapten and xanthotoxin rutin. The flavonoids include quercetin; coumarins include bergapten, daphnoretin, isoimperatorin, naphthoherniarin, psoralen, pangelin, rutamarin, rutarin, scopoletin and umbelliferone.

Garden Rue**Herb**

It is better if the plant is used externally. Used as an emmenagogue, in hysterical conditions, cough and croupy affections, colic and flatulence.

Leaf

Externally, used for sciatica, headache, and muscular chest pain, bronchitis and arthritic conditions. Not to be consumed internally as Fresh juice of leaves, can lead to painful irritations of the stomach and intestines. (*Tesaro de plants*)

Oil

Antispasmodic, antiepileptic, emmenagogue, rubefacient. (Is Toxic in large doses)

INDIAN RHODODENDRON

Melastoma malabathricum

Family: Melastomataceae

Habitat: Moist parts of India, up to 1800 m.

English name: Indian Rhododendron

Local: कुमुल, कीकंद

Figure 3: Indian Rhododendron

Ayurvedic:

Laakheri, Paalorey (Maharashtra). Tulasi (Nepal). Nakkukappan (Tamil Nadu), Phutuka (Assam).

General description:

Shrubs are 1.3 m tall and stem densely covered with paleaceous pectinate hairs. Leaves are elliptic-oblong, base attenuate, apex acute, upper surface prominently lineolate; lower surface tomentose, 5-ribbed, drying dull-greenish; petiole to 1.5 cm long and flowers are solitary.

Silvicultural characteristics: The plant demands full sun and high water preference, maintenance is low.

Indian Rhododendron

Chemical constituents:

Camino acids glycine, valine, leucine, aspartic acid, glutamic acid, methionine, tyrosine, isoleucine and hydroxyproline. The roots gave beta-sitosterol and a triterpene, melastomic acid. (*Medicinal plants, IUCN*)

Medicinal use:

Used to treat diarrhoea, dysentery, haemorrhoids, cuts and wounds, toothache, and stomach-ache.

Leaf

Antidiarrheal, antiseptic. Locally applied in smallpox to prevent pox-marks. The leaves have amino acids. Flowering top astringent, antileucorrhoeic

Bark

Applied to wounds. Also employed in preparation of gargles.

MIMOSA

Neptunia oleracea

Family: Mimosaceae.

Habitat: Throughout India, in tanks.

English: Mimosa, Touch me not.

Local: छुई मुई, मिमोसा, लज्जावंती

Ayurvedic: Lajjaalu, Alabushaa, Siddha, Sadai, Sundaikkirai

Figure 4: Mimosa

General description:

A terrestrial, annual or perennial plant sometimes erect, reaching 20 to 50 cm, sometimes up to 1 m high. The leaves are sensitive and close when touched. The leaves are compound, alternate, on the top of a petiole, 2 to 6 cm long. The flowers are grouped in pink balls at the end of a stalk at the base of the leaves. The fruits are agglomerated flat pods, composed of 3 to 4 articles and with long stiff hairs on the edge.

Silvicultural characteristics:

It is recommended to soak the seeds 24 hours in water. Press the seeds into the soil and lightly cover with an inch of well-draining, loamy soil can tolerate temperatures ranging from 60 degrees to 85 degrees easily if they have the right humidity surrounding them.

Regeneration:

It reproduces by seeds. Seed germinate within 2 weeks.

Chemical constituents:

Alkaloids, flavonoid C-glycosides, sterols, terenoids, tannins, saponin and fatty acids". The roots

of the plant have been shown to contain up to 10% tannin.

Medicinal use:

M. pudica root methanolic extract showed very good wound healing activity, it also showed antimicrobial property, the anti-diarrhoeal potential of the ethanolic extract of leaves of *M. pudica* has been evaluated, contains some vital antiplasmodial constituents such as terpenoids, flavonoids and alkaloids. It also consists of chemicals showing antivenom and antiulcer properties. (*Medicinal plants, IUCN*). Astringent, refrigerant (*Mimosa pudica* Linn. is the accepted source of the classical herb Lajjaalu. It is used as astringent and styptic).

MAST TREE

Polyalthia longifolia

Family: Annonaceae.

Habitat: Native to Sri Lanka; grown in gardens throughout the warmer parts of India.

English: Mast tree, Fake Asoka tree, False Devadaru, Cemetery tree

Local: अशोक-भेड / देवदारु

Figure 5: Mast Tree

Ayurvedic:

Devadaari (Devadaari is equated with *Cedrus deodara*). (An adulterant to the bark of *Saraca asoca*.)

General description:

P. longifolia is a tall evergreen tree with a conical crown. Young branches pilose, becoming glabrous. Leaves are tapering to a fine point, margins undulate, glossy above, glabrous on both

sides (juvenile leaves tomentose).

Silvicultural characteristics:

A light demanding species. A fast-growing species and requires good exposure to sunlight and requires moderate watering.

Mast Tree**Regeneration:**

The seeds do not last long, so that it is usually necessary to plant them as soon as they are ripe. Also, the tree does not withstand transplanting well, so to obtain the best results it is good to plant the seeds directly in the site where the tree is intended to grow.

Chemical constituents:

Bark contains alkaloids, tannins and resins. Leaves contain an azafluorene alkaloid, polylongine, and three aporphine N-oxide alkaloids, (+)-0-methyl-bulbocapnine-8-N-oxide, (+)-0-methyl-bulbocapnine-8-N-oxide and (+)-N-methylnandigernine-B-N-oxide. (Medicinal Plants, IUCN)

Medicinal use:

Bark is used as febrifuge. The plant is useful in the treatment of hysteria, influenza, oedema, respiratory troubles, inflammation, fever, skin disease, diabetes, and hypertension and worm infestation.

The stem bark contains clerodane diterpenes causing febrifuge, cardiac depression.

MYSORE CLOCKVINE

Thunbergia mysorensis

Family: Acanthaceae

Habitat: Native to India, found mostly in southern India

English: Mysore clockvine, Brick & Butter Vine, Lady's Slipper Vine, Dolls' Shoes

Local: झुंबर

General description:

Evergreen twinning vine that grows 16-25 feet tall and at least as wide, with a dense covering of dark green, opposite, lanceolate, acuminate, dentate leaves, 4 to 6 inches long, prominently three-nerved.

Figure 6: Mysore Clock wine

Silvicultural characteristics:

With the right climate, care is simple. It needs average soil that drains well, regular watering, sunny to partially shady, and something to climb. Higher humidity is ideal, so if growing indoors, use a humidity tray or spritz your vine regularly.

Regeneration:

For Cuttings, remove sections of stem that are about 10 cm. Take the cuttings in spring or early summer. Use a rooting hormone and place the cuttings in soil mixed with compost.

Chemical constituents:

India, used to treat coughs, jaundice, liver disease, fever. Phyto-chemical screening yielded protein, alkaloid, amino acid, carbohydrate, flavonoids, tannin, and phenolics.

Medicinal use:

Has an antioxidant potential. Results suggest a good source of natural antioxidants. Antibacteria / Flowers: Antibacterial activity against *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, and *P. aeruginosa*

REFERENCE:

1. Baby Joseph 5(2):41-44, International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Drug Research
2. Brandle, J. E., Starratt, A. N. and Gijzen, M. 1998. *Stevia rebaudiana*: Its agricultural, biological, and chemical properties. *Can. J. Plant Sci.* 78: 527–536
3. C.P.Khare. (2007). *Indian Medicinal Plants*. New Delhi: Springer.

4. Flower Auro. (2023). Retrieved from Flowerauro: <https://www.floweraura.com/blog/everything-you-need-to-know-about-parijat-flowers>
5. Gardening know how. (2023). Retrieved from Gardening know how: <https://www.gardeningknowhow.com/edible/herbs/rue/growing-rue-herb.html>
6. Heuzé V., Tran G., Archimède H., 2019. Mango (*Mangifera indica*) forage. Feedipedia, a programme by INRAE, CIRAD, AFZ and FAO. <https://www.feedipedia.org/node/129> Last updated on July 31, 2019, 18:17
7. Int. J. Pharm. Sci. Rev. Res., 54(2), January - February 2019; Article No. 10, Pages: 51-57.
8. THESAURUS OF MEDICINAL PLANTS . (n.d.). Retrieved from Medicinal Plants: <http://webserv.fq.edu.uy/tematres/vocab/index.php>

AJPHR is
Peer-reviewed
monthly
Rapid publication
Submit your next manuscript at
editor@ajphr.com / editor.ajphr@gmail.com